

LINGVISTIK (LISONIY) TUSHUNCHANING SAMARALI O'ZLASHISHINI TA'MINLAYDIGAN METODIK SHARTLAR

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Lingvistik (lisoniy) tushunchaning samarali o'zlashishini ta'minlaydigan metodik shartlar tahlil qilingan. Mualliflar taxlil yuzasidan ayrim xulosalarga erishgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: grammatik tushuncha, suhbat metodi, muammolimetod, induktiv metod, deduktiv metod, analiz-sintez metodi, lingvistik munosabat, ko'rgazmalilik, grammatik mashq.

METHODOLOGICAL CONDITIONS THAT ENSURE THE EFFECTIVE ACQUISITION OF LINGUISTIC (LINGUISTIC) UNDERSTANDING

Abstract. This article analyzes the methodological conditions that ensure the effective acquisition of Linguistic (linguistic) concepts. The authors have reached some conclusions about the analysis.

Key words: grammatical concept, conversation method, problem method, inductive method, deductive method, analysis-synthesis method, linguistic attitude, demonstration, grammatical exercise.

МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ, ОБЕСПЕЧИВАЮЩИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОЕ ПРИБРЕТЕНИЕ ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОГО (ЯЗЫКОВОГО) ПОНИМАНИЯ.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются методические условия, обеспечивающие эффективное усвоение языковых (лингвистических) понятий. Авторы пришли к некоторым выводам по поводу анализа.

Ключевые слова: грамматическая концепция, разговорный метод, проблемный метод, индуктивный метод, дедуктивный метод, метод анализа-синтеза, языковая установка, демонстрация, грамматическое упражнение.

Bilimni o'zlashtirishning natijasi tushunchani ko'rgazmali o'rganish ma'lumdarajada o'qitish metodlariga bog'liqdir. Grammatik tushunchani shakllantirishda izlanish metodidan foydalanish samarali hisoblanadi. Talabalardan muammoli vaziyat, uning ahamiyati haqida "Pedagogika" dan o'rganilganlari so'rab, esga olinadi. 3- sinfdan "So'z yasovchi qo'shimchalar" mavzusini o'rganish namunasi bayon qilinadi.

Gul gulchi

Traktor traktorchi

Paxta paxtazor

Topshiriq:

1. So'zlarni diqqat bilan o'qing, ma'nolaridagi farqni o'ylab ko'ring.
2. SHu so'zlarning ma'nosini farqlashga xizmat qilayotgan qismni o'ylab toping.

Savol javobdan so'ng o'quvchilar o'z xulosalarini aytadilar. O'qituvchi ularning javoblarini yakunlaydi. Bu metoddan orfografik qoidalar o'rganilganda ham foydalanish mumkin.

Demak, darsda til faktlarini kuzatish metodidan foydalanganda, muammoli vaziyat yaratiladi, o'quvchilar til hodisalarini tahlil qilish, taqqoslash kabi aqliy faoliyatlarini bajaradilar.

O'quvchilarda so'z va gapga lingvistik munosabat nazariy bilimlarni o'zlashtirish, mavhum tafakkurni o'stirish jarayonida shakllantiriladi, tilning semantik va grammatik tomonining bir-biriga ta'sirini anglashni bildiradi.

O'quvchilar tilni ularda til birliklarini ya'ni, so'z, morfema, so'z birikmasi, gapga lingvistik munosabatni parallel shakllantirish bilan birga ongli o'zlashtiradilar.

So'zga lingvistik munosabat so'zni tovush tomondan tahlil qilib, uning tovush va grafik tomoni o'rtasidagi bog'lanishni aniqlash, so'zni morfemik tahlil qilish vaso'zga leksik ma'no berishda morfemaning rolini tushunish, so'zni grammatik tahlil qilish va muayyan so'z turkumiga oid ekani bilan uning grammatik belgilari o'zaro bog'liqligini tushunish ko'nikmasini shakllanishiga qarab o'sib boradi.

Lingvistik munosabat o'quvchilarda asta – sekin shakllantirib boriladi, ularda bilish, tushunib olish saviyasi ham har xil bo'ladi. Masalan, so'z birikmasida so'zlarning o'zaro munosabati.

Tushunchani o'zlashtirish bilimni nutq tajribasiga tatbiq etishning muhim sharti hisoblanadi. Tushunchalar orasidagi bog'lanishni vujudga keltirish, amalga oshirish o'quvchilar o'zbek tilidan egallaydigan bilimlar tizimiga hamda tildan ongli foydalanishga poydevor bo'ladi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari o'zlashtiradigan asosiy bog'lanish yo'llaridan birini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Maktab dasturi lingvistik materialni o'rganishda yangi o'rganilgan materialning ilgarigi o'rganilganlar bilan bog'lanishini ko'zda tutadi. Bu o'rinda talabalardan misollar keltirish so'raladi.

Ayrim til kategoriyalari bog'lanishning mohiyati yangi til kategoriyasini o'rganish jarayonida ochiladi. Masalan, so'zning leksik ma'nosi va uning morfemik tarkibi so'zning ma'noli qismlarini o'rganish jarayonida bir yo'la muhokama qilinadi, chunki morfemaning ahamiyatini boshqacha yo'l billantushuntirib bo'lmaydi. Masalan, ishchi-ishla, ishchan.

Bilish komponentlari o'rtasidagi bog'laniishni aniqlash, bilimni tajribaga, o'quvchilarning yozma va og'zaki nutqiga tatbiq etish imkoniyatini beradi.

Ta'lim jarayonida ko'rgazmaning qanday ahamiyati bor?

2. Ko'rgazmalar tayyorlashda nimalar hisobga olinadi? Savollarga talabalardan olingan javoblar xulosalanadi.

Tushunchani shakllantirish jarayonida ham ko'rgazmalardan foydalaniladi. Bunda jadval, sxema, biror predmet va uning rasmi hamda muayyan til materialiningo'zidan foydalaniladi. O'zakdosh so'zlarni o'rganishda qo'llanadigan ko'rgazma namoyish qilinadi. Ko'rgazma turlaridan maqsadga muvofiq foydalanish kerak.

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